

Title: A realistic outlook on Blockchain's future in the financial sector

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INTRODUCTION:

With the seemingly endless proposed use cases for blockchain technology and recent enterprise adoption of blockchain projects it becomes important to step back and separate good blockchain use cases from bad.

AIM:

This talk highlights realistic and unrealistic applications of blockchain technology within modern day's transaction ecosystem, specifically centered around both private and enterprise blockchain applications in the financial sector.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Research papers from institutions like Deloitte and IBM have proposed that blockchain use cases like cross border payments, after hours trading, and real-time fraud detection are currently within striking distance of numerous financial institutions. In reality, given the current issues with transaction scalability and transactor confidentiality, mass adoption of these use cases are further away than they seem.

RESULTS:

Due to current issues with scalability, confidentiality, and fault tolerance we are actually further than it may seem from the much-discussed utopian transaction ecosystem. As of right now, there are only a few feasible blockchain use cases that can easily be adopted by financial institutions. Until there are more scalable mechanisms in place we will not be able to produce industrial size blockchain use cases that can be utilized without compromising blockchain integrity.

CONCLUSIONS:

This exploration will leave audience members with an understanding of the mechanisms that govern private and enterprise blockchains, as well as an understanding of good and bad use cases and technical factors that will affect blockchain's growth in the financial sector

KEYWORDS:

Blockchain Use Cases; Blockchain Scalability; Blockchain Solutions in Finance

BIOGRAPHY:

Wesley Graham is a student at UC Berkeley, and officer for Blockchain at Berkeley, the US' largest collegiate blockchain organization. Wesley is an industry expert with a background in blockchain use cases, ICO consulting, product analysis, and enterprise blockchain applications. Wesley is additionally involved in leading executive education projects, and has been recognized as a TEDx Speaker, United Nations Youth Ambassador, and BC Excellence Award winner. In his free time, he can be found on LinkedIn building hype about Disruptive Technologies, organizing major hackathons, or at a basketball game cheering wildly.